

FRACTURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH TRANSVERSE CRACK-TIP DELAMINATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The transverse-crack-tip delamination problem has been studied using the fracture mechanics approach. The problem was formulated based on a variational principle consistent higher order plate theory which includes both the transverse shear effect and thickness-stretch deformation. A closed form of strain energy release rate was derived by the analytical approach. Finite element method was also used to analyze the local delamination problem and calculate the energy release rate by three different techniques. For laminates [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s ($n=3,4,6,8$) subjected to tensile load, the critical energy release rates calculated from the analytical method and the finite element method show excellent agreement. The critical stresses calculated by the analytical method are in good agreement with the test data for laminates [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s with $n=3,4,6,8$.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination between composite layers is a critical failure mode for laminated composite structures. Usually, regions with geometric discontinuities, such as free edges, cutouts, holes, ply terminations and voids, are prone to induce delamination under both static and cyclic loadings. The gradients of interlaminar normal and shear stresses become very high near these sites due to the mismatch in Poisson's ratios and shear-extension coupling coefficients of individual plies. Two different types of delamination, edge delamination and local delamination, have been observed and studied [1,2]. Edge delamination typically occurs at the load-free edge of the laminate between 90° plies and adjacent angle plies. The shape of this type of delamination looks like a thumbnail initially and rapidly becomes a strip delamination along the lengthwise loading direction and grows towards the center of the laminate along the width direction with increasing loading. On the other hand, the across-the-width local delamination which is also called transverse-crack-tip delamination, typically occurs at the matrix crack tip between ply interface where complex interlaminar stresses exist. These interlaminar stresses cause the formation of local delamination and may drive it to grow along the lengthwise loading direction. Local delaminations can be initiated at different sites of matrix crack tips and combined together during the delamination growth process to form a global delamination until the final failure occurs due to fiber fracture in the primary load-carrying plies. The formation and growth of both edge and local delaminations will reduce the stiffness and strength of composite laminates. Simple and accurate methods

are necessary in assessing the stiffness and strength degradations for effective and reliable design of composite structures.

In the present work, the transverse-crack-tip induced local delamination of $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminates with $n = 3, 4, 6, 8$ has been studied using a fracture mechanics approach. One analytical model and one finite element model - plane strain model, are adopted to study this problem. In the analytical approach, a variational-principle-consistent higher order plate theory [3] which includes both the transverse shear deformation and thickness-stretching deformation is used to formulate the problem. The theory is equivalent to the modified version of Whitney-Sun laminated plate theory [4] and has been used by Pagano [5] to calculate the free-edge interlaminar normal stress. With thickness-stretching deformation considered in the present model, the interlaminar stresses at the delamination front can be obtained analytically. Although the calculated interlaminar stresses become very large near the delamination front, they remain to be finite and there is no stress singularity. It is noticed that the interlaminar normal and shear stresses obtained from the analysis may not exactly match those obtained from the finite element methods with or without using special free-edge elements. For the present method, since the traction-free edge conditions are satisfied merely in the sense of weighted integral based on the displacement type variational principle, the calculated interlaminar stresses may contain large errors in the pointwise values near the delamination front. Nevertheless, the interlaminar stress distributions obtained from this model can be viewed as an approximation of the real stress field. As mentioned in Reference 6, since the stress singularity at the delamination front is not physically realistic, some variables other than the interlaminar stresses which are finite at the delamination front may be more appropriate in representing the fracture behavior of delaminated laminate by a global sense. The energy release rate is a generic parameter to characterize the fracture behavior of the delaminated laminate. It represents a global rather than a local quantity of the delaminated laminate. Although the interlaminar stresses calculated from the present model may not be accurate near the delamination front, the strain energy release rate calculated from the present model is accurate which can be used to study the local delamination problem with the fracture mechanics approach. A closed form of strain energy release rate can be derived by taking the delamination length as one of the variational quantities in the variational principle. A two-dimensional plane strain finite element model is also developed to study the transverse crack induced local delamination problem. From the finite element results, three different methods - the J-integral method, the compliance method, and the virtual crack closure technique, are used to calculate the strain energy release rate and compared with those calculated by the analytical approach. Excellent agreements are obtained among these four different methods. The critical stresses at the onset of local delamination and the ultimate laminate failure based on the thickness-stretching shear deformation theory (TSSDT) have been obtained and compared with the testing data. Results are in good agreement with the testing data for $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ laminates with $n = 3, 4, 6, 8$.

ANALYTICAL APPROACH

The local delamination behavior of $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminates with $n = 3, 4, 6, 8$ is analyzed by the thickness-stretching shear deformation theory (TSSDT). Equidistance transverse matrix cracks developed in the 90° plies are assumed in the current model and the delaminations are assumed to grow from both ends of the transverse crack tip. A longitudinal section of the geometric configuration is illustrated in Figure 1. Consider the symmetry of the configuration, the geometric model of the transverse-crack-tip local delamination is shown in Figure 2. Since an across-the-width delamination is assumed, the problem can be treated by a one-dimensional model. Both the transverse crack and the delamination are

considered as traction-free boundaries. The model has been divided into three spanwise regions which include one integral region and two delaminated regions. These three regions are referred as base sublaminates (sublaminates 1), lower sublaminates (sublaminates 2), and upper sublaminates (sublaminates 3) respectively (see Figure 2). The layups in these three sublaminate are $[\pm 25/90_n]$, $[90_n]$ and $[\pm 25]$ respectively. A brief description of TSSDT model is given below. A more detailed derivation can be found in Reference 3.

For one-dimensional first order shear deformation theory with thickness-stretching deformation mode, the in-plane displacement u and transverse displacement w are both linear functions of the z -coordinate and can be defined as follows:

$$u(x,z) = u^0(x) + z \psi(x) \tag{1}$$

$$w(x,z) = w^0(x) + z \varphi(x) \tag{2}$$

where u^0 and w^0 are the inplane and transverse displacements at the midplane of the plate, ψ is the rotation, and φ is the thickness strain in the z -coordinate. Let a and L be the lengths of the delaminated segment and the whole model, respectively, and h and H be the thicknesses of the upper sublaminates and the base sublaminates, respectively. Due to the symmetry at the midplane of the laminate $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$, the geometric constraints at the midplanes of the base sublaminates and lower sublaminates are

$$w_1 = 0 \quad \text{for } a \leq x \leq L, z_1 = -H/2 \tag{3}$$

$$w_2 = 0 \quad \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq a, z_2 = -(H-h)/2 \tag{4}$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 represent the corresponding sublaminate. The constraint relations between w^0 and φ in sublaminate 1 and 2 can be obtained from Eqs. (3) and (4) as:

$$w_1^0(x) = \frac{H}{2} \varphi_1(x) \quad \text{for } a \leq x \leq L \tag{5}$$

$$w_2^0(x) = \frac{H-h}{2} \varphi_2(x) \quad \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq a \tag{6}$$

Thus, in each of the sublaminate 1 and 2, there are three equilibrium equations. However, there are four equilibrium equations in sublaminates 3 to determine the four displacement variables u_3^0 , w_3^0 , ψ_3 and φ_3 . Altogether ten equations of equilibrium with the associated natural boundary conditions can be derived by the variational energy principle based on a one-dimensional thickness-stretching shear deformation theory. The energy release rate G can also be obtained from the variational principle by taking the delamination length a as one of the variational quantities. The governing equations of the local delamination problem consist of the three sets of equilibrium equations in sublaminate 1, 2 and 3, the geometric (symmetric) boundary conditions, the traction boundary conditions, and the continuity conditions at the interfaces of the sublaminate. The distributions of interlaminar normal and shear stresses in the region near the delamination front and the energy release rate can be found from the solution of this boundary value problem.

FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

A plane strain finite element model is developed to study the local delamination behavior of $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminates with $n = 3,4,6,8$ in simple tension. The same local delamination configuration shown in Figure 2 is used in the finite element model. PDA PATRAN 3.0 is used to create this geometric model and element mesh, and the finite element

code ABAQUS is adopted for the stress analysis. Iso-parametric 2-D plane strain 8-node biquadratic elements are used in the model with two elements per ply thickness. These second order elements are more efficient than 4-node constant strain elements in handling high stress gradients. Coincident nodes with different node numbers are used along the delamination surface to simulate the delamination between the -25 degree and 90 degree plies.

There are various methods can be used to calculate the energy release rate. It is known that sharp cracks exhibit an elastic strain singularity of order $1/\sqrt{r}$ at the crack tip, and the second order elements can have such a strain term in their basis if they are focussed on the crack tip and if the mid-side nodes on the edge radiating out from the crack tip are placed at one quarter of the distance from the crack tip to the other node on that edge. Such a mesh near the delamination front was used and is shown in Figure 3. The J-Integral evaluation G_J provided by ABAQUS can then be obtained by using this particular mesh. The energy release rate can also be calculated by compliance method using a central difference approximation as follows:

$$G_c = \frac{P}{8} \frac{u_1^0(L) \Big|_{a+\Delta a} - u_1^0(L) \Big|_{a-\Delta a}}{\Delta a} \tag{7}$$

where $u_1^0(L) \Big|_{a+\Delta a}$ is the axial displacement at $x = L$ for delamination length $a + \Delta a$. The third method to calculate the strain energy release rate is based on the virtual crack closure technique [7]. Figure 4 illustrates the technique as it was used in the finite element analysis. First, the nodal forces were calculated at a configuration with delamination length a . Then, the delamination was extended an amount Δa and the resulting nodal displacements at the same location were calculated. The mode I (open mode) and mode II (slide mode) components of the energy release rate are calculated by the following equations:

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \left[\left(Z_b^1 + Z_b^2 \right) \left(w_b - w_c \right) + Z_d^2 \left(w_d - w_e \right) \right] \tag{8}$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \left[\left(Y_b^1 + Y_b^2 \right) \left(v_b - v_c \right) + Y_d^2 \left(v_d - v_e \right) \right] \tag{9}$$

where Y_b^i and Z_b^i represent the nodal forces before delamination extension in the y and z directions at node b calculated from i -th element, and v_b and w_b are the nodal displacements in the y and z directions at node b after delamination extension (see Figure 4). The sum of G_I and G_{II} is the total energy release rate G_{VCCCT} , thus

$$G_{VCCCT} = G_I + G_{II} \tag{10}$$

Based on TSSDT, Chen and Ronnau [3] have derived a closed form of the strain energy release rate which can be used to calculate the critical energy release rates G_{TSSDT} at the onset of delamination and at ultimate tensile strengths. Energy release rate from all four different approaches have been calculated and compared. For finite element analysis, a mesh of 180 elements is used as it yielded a convergent and acceptable solution.

The reduced stiffness which is the stiffness of the delaminated laminate can be calculated from the finite element result by the following equation:

$$E_{re} = \frac{\sigma_0 L}{u(L)} \tag{11}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crossman and Wang [1] have performed tension tests on T300/934 graphite/epoxy [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates with the values of n taken as 1/2, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 8. In their tests, two distinct types of delamination were observed, namely, free edge delamination and local delamination. The free edge delamination was observed to initiate at the load-free edges of the coupon for $n \leq 2$ and the local delamination was initiated at the interface of -25/90 plies across the entire width of the coupon caused by a transverse matrix crack in the 90-deg ply for $n \geq 3$. The stresses at the onset of delamination and the ultimate tensile strengths for various [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates have been recorded by Crossman and Wang [1]. For local delamination problem, these recorded stresses for $n = 3, 4, 6, 8$ are used to calculate the applied loads in the present analysis. The critical energy release rates at the onset of delamination for [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates with $n \geq 3$ using the four different methods described in the previous section are listed in Table 1. It is shown that the critical energy release rates obtained from these four methods are very close to each other. Among these four critical energy release rates, three of them (G_T , G_C , and G_{VCCT}) are calculated from the finite element method and G_{TSSDT} is evaluated from TSSDT. The excellent agreement between G_{TSSDT} and other three energy release rates from finite element result shows that the model based on TSSDT is a valid analytical method to study the delamination problem.

It is noticed that, if fracture toughness is the key failure factor for the onset of delamination and failure of composite laminates, then the energy release rates at these two states for [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates are expected to be constants for different values of n. As expected, results in Table 1 show that the energy release rates for [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates with $n = 3, 4, 6$ and 8 which calculated from the finite element method and the TSSDT model are very close to each other at the ultimate failure of composite laminates. This indicates that the critical energy release rate (or fracture toughness) for the ultimate failure of composite laminates exists. Similar results are also obtained for the onset of delamination.

The energy release rate at the onset of delamination for [$\pm 25/90_8$]_s laminate is found to be 88.76 Nm/m² based on TSSDT model. If this value is assumed as the critical value G_C , then the stress σ_c at the onset of delamination for [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates with $n \neq 8$ can be predicted by TSSDT. Comparisons of the calculated critical stresses based on TSSDT with the testing data from Crossman and Wang [1] are shown in Table 2. It is seen that the analytical results are in excellent agreements with the testing data. Similar results for ultimate failure stress can also be obtained.

From finite element solution, typical interlaminar normal and shear stress distributions for [$\pm 25/90_4$]_s laminate ahead of the delamination front are shown in Figures 5 and 6. In these figures, very high normal and shear stresses are observed at the delamination front. These behaviors are qualitatively the same as those obtained from TSSDT model [3]. The variations of energy release rate G with the normalized delamination length a/L for different [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates ($n = 3, 4, 6, 8$) are shown in Figure 7. It is seen that, except at the two end regions where the values of a/L close to 0 and 1 (which are the invalid regions of plate model), the

Table 1 Energy release rates at ultimate tensile stresses for [$\pm 25/90_n$]_s laminates using four different methods ($a = 0.004064$ m, and $L = 0.016256$ m)

n	σ_o (MPa)	G_T (N/m)	G_C (N/m)	G_{VCCT} (N/m)	G_{TSSDT} (N/m)
3	292.0	97.84	-	97.84	98.35
4	211.0	93.77	93.65	93.62	94.03
6	140.0	101.10	-	101.10	101.36
8	101.0	101.43	-	101.43	101.59

Table 2 Critical stresses at onset of delamination for $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ laminates (critical energy release rate = 88.76 Nm/m^2)

n	σ_{cr} (MPa) (TSSDT)	σ_{cr} (MPa) (test)
3	277.2	270.0
4	205.0	211.0
6	131.0	128.0
8	94.4	94.4

energy release rate is almost a constant. The reductions of stiffness with the delamination length for different $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ laminates ($n = 3, 4, 6, 8$) are also calculated from the finite element results and shown in Figure 8.

CONCLUSION

Based on TSSDT, a closed form of the strain energy release rate has been obtained. A finite element model has also been developed to study the transverse-crack-tip induced delamination problem and to verify the analytical TSSDT model [3]. Three different methods - the J-integral method, the compliance method, and the virtual crack closure technique, are used to calculate the strain energy release rate from the finite element solution. The strain energy release rate is also calculated by the closed form TSSDT. Excellent agreements obtained from all four different methods. These agreements indicates that the model based on TSSDT is a valid analytical method to study the delamination problem. For $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminates under simple tension, critical stresses at the onset of local delamination and the ultimate laminate failure based on the TSSDT have been obtained and compared with the testing data. Results are in good agreement with the testing data for $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ laminates with $n = 3, 4, 6, 8$.

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Fig. 1 Longitudinal cross section of local delamination

Fig. 2 Geometric model of local delamination

Figure 3. - Crack tip finite element mesh

Figure 4. - Virtual crack closure method for calculating strain energy release rates

Figure 5. - Interlaminar normal stress distribution ahead of delamination front for $[\pm 25/90_4]_s$ laminate ($\sigma=211$ MPa)

Figure 6. - Interlaminar shear stress distribution ahead of delamination front for $[\pm 25/90_4]_s$ laminate ($\sigma=211$ MPa)

Figure 7. - Variation of energy release rate with delamination length for $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ laminates

Figure 8. - Variation of reduced stiffness with delamination length for $[\pm 25/90_n]_s$ laminates